

LIFE-CYCLE ASSESSMENT OF JOINTED PLAIN CONCRETE PAVEMENTS WITH GFRP BARS

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ABSTRACT

Traditional building materials, such as concrete and steel, consume vast amounts of natural resources and energy. Glass fiber-reinforced polymer (GFRP) dowel bars are a non-corrodible alternative to conventional steel in jointed plain concrete pavements (JPCP). However, in order to promote the same load transfer efficiency between pavement slabs, it is necessary to use a greater number of GFRP bars with a larger diameter. Thus, to analyze FRP's potential sustainability, a life-cycle assessment of JPCP with steel and GFRP dowels is performed. Finally, GFRP bars are a satisfactory alternative to steel considering the impacts associated with the construction and maintenance of JPC pavements.

KEYWORDS

GFRP dowel bars, jointed plain concrete pavements, life-cycle assessment.

INTRODUCTION

Transfer bars transmit the load between concrete slabs in rigid pavements without restricting horizontal movement caused by contractions and expansions derived from moisture and temperature effects (Maitra et al., 2009). Thus, the use of transfer bars contributes significantly to a higher load transfer efficiency (LTE) and significantly reduces critical problems arising from faulting and pumping effects (Larson & Smith, 2005; Vijay et al., 2009).

Historically, transfer bars used in rigid pavements are made of carbon steel, but this material quickly begins to corrode when exposed to weather and especially when in contact with chlorides, whether in coastal areas or when exposed to deicing salts. Corrosion of transfer bars can cause changes in the mechanical behavior of the pavement, reducing its service life (Snyder, 2011). To enhance the durability of steel bars and prevent corrosion, methods such as polymer coating, corrosion inhibitors, and cathodic protection are considered (Galliano & Landolt, 2002; Orlikowski et al., 2004). However, these measures only reduce the speed of corrosion propagation (Duo et al., 2021). Fiber reinforced polymer (FRP) bars, when used as reinforcement in concrete structures, show better durability results when compared to traditional steel bars (Sleiman & Polak, 2020). Due to their resistance to chloride corrosion (Tafsirojjaman et al., 2019) and fatigue, thermal and electrical non-conductivity, and transparency to magnetic fields (ACI 440.3R-12, 2012; ASTM D7957/D7957M, 2017), they are used in rigid pavements as transfer bars to transfer forces transmit forces between pavement slabs (Montaigu et al., 2013).

Nevertheless, according to literature studies, the use of FRP bars as transfer bars in place of conventional steel results in higher stresses in the contact region between the bar and concrete and higher relative vertical displacements between slabs; these facts are usually justified by the low elastic modulus of polymer bars (Cable & Porter, 2003; Murison et al., 2005; Snyder, 2011; Vijay et al., 2009). Thus, to obtain the same LTE of rigid pavements with steel link bars, it is recommended to apply less spaced and larger diameter FRP bars (Snyder, 2011).

Furthermore, the feasibility of using FRP bars on the grounds of sustainability can be questioned in relation to the environmental impacts associated with their production, use, and disposal. However, previous studies comparing the use of FRP bars to steel bars indicated a reduction in environmental impacts (Garg & Shrivastava, n.d.; Inman et al., 2017; Işildar et al., 2020; Katz, 2004). In general, it is assumed that, in concrete pavements, the total mass of FRP bars required is approximately four times smaller than that of steel to obtain the same structural results (Işildar et al., 2020), and since they do not require covering to avoid corrosion, the volume of concrete required for the pavement can also be reduced, further minimizing environmental impacts (Katz, 2004).

Nevertheless, adequate design for the use of FRP bars in place of steel as non-corrosive, high-durability transfer bars, and the impact of this pavement must be better analyzed. Thus, this work presents a life cycle analysis and environmental impact of rigid pavements with conventional steel reinforcement and FRP bars, taking into account their design, material production and construction.

METHODOLOGY

Concrete slab thickness calculation

In this study, we consider unidirectional rigid pavements with two distinct material transfer bars to be build in São Paulo, Brazil. In order to design the concrete slab itself, we followed the rigid pavement design manuals from the Municipality of São Paulo (IP-07, 2004) and the National Department of Transportation Infrastructure, DNIT (DNIT IPR-714, 2005). The following assumptions were adopted:

- (i) a light to medium traffic road supported on a granular base (BGS);
- (ii) the value modulus of subgrade reaction was adopted considering an intermediate value of soil resistance (CBR = 10%) and a 15 cm thick base was of 58 MPa/m;
- (iii) the unit wheel was of the TB-450 standard train (7.5 tf per wheel) from the NBR 7188/2013 (ABNT NBR 7188, 2013)
- (iv) no significant thermal variation and only one type of vehicle (and therefore load) on the pavement, the thickness that corresponds to a fatigue resistance capable of withstanding 2×10^6 passes of the equivalent standard axle was determined; and
- (v) a concrete with a characteristic strength (f_{ck}) of 30 MPa was used (characteristic flexural tensile strength ($f_{ctM,k}$) of 5.4 (ABNT NBR 6118, 2014)).

Based on these values, and applying the assumptions of the Portland Cement Association (PCA/84) method presented in DNIT IPR-714 (2005), the adopted minimum concrete slab thickness was 15 cm.

Calculation of dimensions for CA-25 steel transfer bars elements

Considering the contact of the slab with the ground, it is recommended to use a minimum cover of steel reinforcement of 3 to 4 cm. For joint depths between slabs, DNIT IPR-714 (2005) recommends up to 25% of the slab thickness. Therefore, for 15 cm slabs, it is considered that the joint depth will reach 3.75 cm and the transfer bar will be positioned 7.5 cm from the top surface of the pavement, and then at least an additional 1.5 cm of thickness beyond the face of the bar is required. Thus, for 25 mm bars, and keeping the transfer bar position at the center of the slab, it is necessary to add 5 cm to the pavement thickness. With 20 cm thickness, the minimum cover will be 3.75 cm, which is acceptable in terms of durability and compatible with the considered design loads.

The minimum spacing required between the bars was calculated for a transfer percentage of 45%, as indicated in Vijay et al. (2009), and came to 18 cm, for 25 mm diameter bars. It should be noted that the type of joint between the slabs adopted has a significant influence on the design. For this study, contraction joints were considered (Figure 1), which significantly reduce the relative displacement between the slabs, and are modeled considering a reduction in joint thickness (Vijay et al., 2009). Therefore, for CA-25 steel transfer bars, 25 mm diameter bars with a length of 70 cm, spaced every 18 cm, were used.

Figure 1: Contraction joint adopted in the design, where h is the pavement higher and d is the dowel diameter. Adapted from Vijay et al. (2009).

The pavement in this study was considered to a two-lane roadway (7.20 m) without concrete shoulders, compatible with a low to medium traffic flow, requiring two plates positioned contiguously. The longitudinal length of the concrete plate depends mainly on the constituent materials of the concrete and environmental conditions. Following the recommendations in DNIT IPR-714 (2005), plates of 5.00 m in length by 3.60 m in width were adopted.

It should be noted that, in addition to transfer bars, connection bars between contiguous plates are necessary to maintain pavement continuity. As these elements do not transmit loads, they will be defined equally for both plates with steel and GFRP bars. Thus, in this case, 20 mm diameter CA-25 steel bars with a length of 40 cm, spaced every 25 cm, will be used. Based on the assumptions presented, and for 1 km of pavement, a quantity of C30 concrete of 1440 m³ and a quantity of CA-25 steel of 25404 kg was calculated.

Calculation of slab dimensions for GFRP dowel bars

For GFRP reinforced plates, it is not necessary to meet the minimum cover requirement to guarantee the durability of the bars within the concrete. Thus, the slab thickness be maintained as the minimum, previously indicated, of 15 cm. In this case, FRP bars with a diameter of 3.8 cm should be used, so that a joint of 3.75 cm depth (25% of the pavement thickness) can still be cast without reaching the bar, ensuring the existence of a minimum concrete dimension between the joint and the bar (1.9 cm).

Using the same basic design characteristics as in the previous calculation for CA-25 steel bars, but changing the mechanical properties of the material to those of GFRP, the minimum spacing required between transfer bars for a diameter of 38 mm is calculated as 18 cm.

The minimum necessary length for GFRP bars should be compatible with the value of the bond that these bars have with the cementitious matrix, allowing for the complete transfer of forces to the concrete. Evidence found in the literature indicates greater efficiency in transferring stresses from GFRP bars to concrete due to the roughness present on their surface, although the Poisson's effect on tensile bars, more pronounced than on steel bars, may partially negate this effect (Vijay et al., 2009).

Since the GFRP bars designed here mainly act in shear (thus reducing the influence of the Poisson's effect), and as the diameter adopted for this solution is larger than the previous one (less specific surface for stress transfer), it was decided to consider that the effects balance out and adopt the same length for the bars in both solutions.

Therefore, for the transfer bars, 38 mm diameter bars, 70 cm in length, spaced every 18 cm was considered. The size of the plates for this design situation was kept at 5.00 x 3.60 m. For the connecting bars, GFRP bars with a diameter of 20 mm and a length of 40 cm, spaced every 25 cm, were adopted, similar to the previous calculation. Based on the assumptions presented, and for 1 km of pavement, a quantity of C30 concrete of 1080 m³ and a quantity of GFRP bars of 14190 kg were obtained.

Life-cycle assessment

Life cycle assessment (LCA) covers all the processes throughout the lifespan of a product, from the supply of raw materials, through production and assembly, packaging and distribution, installation and use of the product, to final disposal or recycling at the end of its life (Pavlović et al., 2022). As shown in Figure 2, the structure of an LCA consists of four correlated stages: goal and scope definition, inventory analysis, impact assessment, and interpretation (NBR-14.040, 2001). It is important to highlight that an interpretation is conducted at each stage of the LCA, thus the results presented in a life cycle assessment should be interpreted with caution, considering the functional unit and applied boundary conditions, data uncertainty, among other factors.

Figure 2: Phases of a life-cycle assessment. Adapted from NBR-14.040 (2001).

This study used an "attributorial LCA" approach, which aims to describe environmentally relevant physical flows for a life cycle and its subsystems. This means that the environmental impacts of a system in a pre-defined state were quantified, and emissions were calculated without considering indirect effects related to possible changes in the production system. The software SimaPro, version 9.5 was used to model the systems and calculate the environmental impacts of analyzed scenario. The ecoinvent database version 3.9 was applied as source of the life cycle inventory (LCI) data. The ReCiPe 2016 Midpoint Hierarchist (H) calculation methodology was used. More information about this methodology can be found in Hauschild & Huijbregts (2015) and Huijbregts et al. (2017).

The ecoinvent database contains datasets from different sectors and regions. In the present study, when a process was not available in the database, a custom process was created using SimaPro and literature data. As the pavement was considered to be constructed in Brazil, priority was given to Brazilian-specific data, whenever possible. When it was not possible, Global (RoW/GLO) data was used as a proxy.

The categories considered in this work were: Global Warming Potential (GWP), Stratospheric Ozone Depletion (SOD), Ionising Radiation (IR), Ozone Formation Human Health (OFHH), Fine Particulate Matter Formation (FPMF), Ozone Formation Terrestrial Ecosystems (OFTE), Terrestrial Acidification (TA), Freshwater Eutrophication (FEu), Marine Eutrophication (MEu), Terrestrial Ecotoxicity (TEc), Freshwater Ecotoxicity (FEc), Marine Ecotoxicity (MEc), Human Carcinogenic Toxicity (HCT),

Human Non-Carcinogenic Toxicity (HNCT), Land Use (LU), Mineral Resource Scarcity (MRS, Fossil Resource Scarcity (FRS) and Water Consumption (WC).

LCA objective and scope

The definition of objective and scope is the first stage of the life cycle assessment (LCA) process. This stage involves defining the purpose and boundaries of the assessment, including the intended application of the results, the functional unit of analysis, and the system boundaries. The functional unit is the quantified performance measure of the product or service being assessed, while the system boundaries determine which processes and inputs are included in the assessment. The objective and scope definition should be transparent, clear, and consistent, and should involve input from relevant stakeholders.

In this study, we consider cradle-to-end of life of rigid pavements with FRP and steel dowel bars considering a 70-year service life, which accounts for production of the bars and concrete (consumed energy and resources), building, use and maintenance (considering degradation by steel corrosion) of the pavement. This study does not consider waste in the pavement production process, transportation of bars and concrete, and recycling activities of the materials involved in the production process.

Inventory

Table 1 presents the materials used in the life cycle assessment of this study. For the production of GFRP reinforcement bars, the use of 70% glass fibers and 30% epoxy resin was considered based on the final mass of the bar. In the pultrusion process, 3.1 MJ per kg of material was considered based on studies reported in the literature (Jauhari et al., 2015; Suzuki & Takahashi, 2005). For modeling concrete and steel, existing processes in the "Environmental Footprint" database described in Table 1 were used.

Table 1: Materials used in the life cycle analysis.

Material	Constituent	Process nomenclature
GFRP	Epoxy resin	Epoxy resin, liquid (RoW) market for epoxy resin, liquid Cut-off, S
	Fiber	Glass fibre {RoW} glass fibre production cut-off, S
	Electricity	Electricity, low voltage {BR} market group for electricity, low voltage Cut-off, S
Conventional Steel	Process	Reinforcing steel {RoW} reinforcing steel production Cut-off, S
Galvanised steel	Process	Zinc coat, pieces, adjustment per micro-m {RoW} zinc coating, pieces, adjustment per micro-m Cut-off, U
	Process	Reinforcing steel {RoW} reinforcing steel production Cut-off, S
Stainless steel	Process	Steel, chromium steel 18/8 {RoW} steel production, electric, chromium steel 18/8 Cut-off, S
Concrete	Process	Concrete, 30 MPa (BR) for building construction, with cement CP-II-E Cut-off S

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Figure 3 shows a comparison of the environmental impacts associated with producing the required quantity of the analyzed dowels necessary for the pavements construction. The graph presents the relative results of the impact indicators for each variant of the design. For each indicator, the maximum result is defined as 100%, and the results of the other variant are displayed in relation to it. It was observed that, in the production phase, the stainless steel showed the major impact in the most of the categories. However, the GFRP dowels also showed a great emission rate comparing with the other alternatives. When it comes to stratospheric ozone depletion, the GFRP dowels production provides the

greatest impact. Furthermore, in the category of global warming, GFRP dowels were the second alternative that showed the greatest impact.

Figure 4 shows the comparison between the environmental impacts associated with the construction of the rigid pavement with steel and GFRP transfer bars until the end of life. To consider the maintenance activities of conventional steel due to the corrosion, the same premise adopted by Katz (2004), based on the studies of Ehlen (1999) and Ehlen & Marshall (1996) was used. According to these previous research, maintenance activities on concrete decks begin 28 years after they are built. Starting with the 28th year and every three years after that, 2.5 percent of the deck's surface is chipped away and the deck is repaired with new materials. This maintenance activity was considered only to pavements with conventional steel dowels, using the premise that the degradation process would not be observed in the pavements with corrosion resistant dowels. However, the concrete quantity previously calculated for the case of conventional steel was also used in the pavements with galvanized steel or stainless steel, i.e., the major concrete cover than in the case of GFRP dowels bars use was maintained. This adopted premise takes into account the fact that when using galvanized steel or stainless steel the corrosion process turns into something slowly but it is not completely dissipated (Bertolini et al., 2013).

It can be observed that, even though the production of GFRP bars is known to have higher environmental impact than conventional steel bars in various important categories (as global warming and ozone depletion), the consideration of pavement degradation by corrosion and necessary maintenance makes the use of steel dowel bars an option with higher environmental impact in all categories analyzed. Also, comparing with the other corrosion resistant materials, the pavements with GFRP dowels showed to be an option with minor impacts in various categories. These results were obtained due to two facts, the maintenance activities in pavements with conventional steel and the major concrete quantity used in the steel reinforced concrete pavements including the galvanized steel and the stainless steel. This shows that, when choosing the most sustainable dowel alternative, the whole life cycle of the JPCP should be considered.

Figure 3: Environmental impacts associated with the production of the necessary amount of the different dowels.

Figure 4: Cradle-to-gate of the pavements with the different reinforcement materials.

CONCLUSIONS

Given the relevance of using GFRP bars in concrete pavements due to the advantages related to durability, this study analyzed the life cycle of concrete pavements with steel, galvanized steel, stainless steel and GFRP dowels. The pavements were designed according to normative recommendations. The analyses performed lead to the following conclusions:

- The use of GFRP bars reduces the consumption of concrete in the construction of pavements, which consequently reduces the impact of constructing pavements with lower expected loads; The anticipated maintenance due to defects caused by the corrosion process that occurs in the conventional steel reinforced concrete reveals a greater benefit from the use of GFRP bars in the environmental impact analysis. However, other degradation mechanisms are associated with the use of polymer bars and should be better analyzed when data on the subject is available in the literature.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request

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